

1 **TITLE:** Concordance between realised and fundamental niches in three Iberian *Sigara*
2 species (Hemiptera: Corixidae) along a gradient of salinity and anionic composition.

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9 **SHORT TITLE:** Realised and fundamental niches in three *Sigara* species.

10
11 **KEYWORDS:** salinity tolerance, anionic composition, niche breadth, *Sigara*, corixids.

12
13 **SUMMARY**

- 14 1. We test the hypothesis that the physiological tolerance of corixids for saline
15 conditions determines, at least partially, their occurrence along a salinity
16 gradient that encompasses a variety of anionic compositions.
- 17 2. Three species of *Sigara*, *S. nigrolineata* (freshwaters), *S. scripta* (hyposaline
18 waters) and *S. selecta* (mesosaline and hypersaline waters) were selected, and it
19 was predicted that species occurring in the most saline waters would be ion-
20 regulation specialists that are more tolerant of higher salinity, while species
21 living in fresh or hyposaline waters would be generalist regulators in relation to
22 different anions, and therefore less tolerant of higher salinity.
- 23 3. Niche breadth was quantified using field data for both water conductivity and
24 anionic composition (realised niche). In addition, physiological tolerance in

25 relation to conductivity and anionic composition (fundamental niche) were
26 estimated in laboratory tests using eggs, nymphs and adults of all species.

27 4. *Sigara nigrolineata* adults showed the most limited conductivity tolerance and
28 were generalists in relation to different anionic water compositions. *Sigara*
29 *scripta* demonstrated tolerance of hyposaline and mesosaline waters and higher
30 survival rates in sulphated waters. *Sigara selecta* was the only species occupying
31 hypersaline waters that showed a preference for anion chloride.

32 5. *Sigara scripta* was the only species coexisting with the other two species. This
33 can be explained by the overlap found in conductivity and anionic composition
34 niche dimensions at the lower (*S. nigrolineata*) and upper (*S. selecta*) tolerance
35 limits.

36 6. Young life-stages of the species showed similar responses but less tolerance of
37 higher salinity than adults; this was the case for eggs of *S. nigrolineata* and
38 nymphs of *S. scripta* and *S. selecta*.

39 7. Physiological limitations were not found in relation to fresh and less saline
40 waters in *S. selecta* so other factors, probably involving biotic interactions, may
41 play an important role in this species.

42

43 INTRODUCTION

44 Understanding how species respond to environmental factors is a central concern of
45 ecology (Chown, 2001). Physiological studies help define the niche breadths of species
46 and improve understanding of their habitat use and geographical ranges (Hoffmann &
47 Blows, 1994; Gaston, 2003; 2009; Calosi *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, physiological
48 information may be used to assess the viability of a population in the face of potential
49 threats like habitat modification, global warming (Bozinovic *et al.*, 2011) or invasions

50 by alien species (Van De Meutter *et al.*, 2010). As a result, many studies have focused
51 on the effects of stressors on species physiology for conservation purposes (e.g. Homan
52 *et al.*, 2003; Kefford *et al.*, 2005; Sánchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2010, Arribas *et al.*, 2012).
53 Water salinity and ionic composition can be natural stressors in aquatic habitats,
54 particularly in arid and semiarid zones such as the Mediterranean basin, where highly
55 mineralised waters are common. In this respect, the south-eastern Iberian Peninsula is
56 one of the most arid European regions and encompasses a wide variety of aquatic
57 ecosystems ranging from freshwater streams, ponds and wetlands to hypersaline
58 streams, saline lagoons and salt pans (Millán *et al.*, 2006, Picazo *et al.*, 2012). Although
59 many of these habitats are found throughout Europe, some saline and hypersaline
60 habitats are unique to this region and host a high number of rare and endemic species,
61 particularly aquatic Coleoptera and Hemiptera (Moreno *et al.*, 1997; Velasco *et al.*,
62 2006; Sanchez-Fernández *et al.*, 2008; Abellán *et al.*, 2009; Millán *et al.*, 2011). Within
63 the Hemiptera, the Corixidae family is the most diversified and well-adapted to aquatic
64 habitats. Specifically, the genus *Sigara* (Fabricius, 1779) includes representative species
65 from freshwaters to saline water bodies (Jansson, 1986) and encompasses a wide
66 salinity gradient in the Iberian Peninsula (Millán *et al.*, 1988; Carbonell *et al.*, 2011).
67 Physiological adaptations to salinity may be an integral part of the evolution, ecology
68 and biogeography of organisms of saline waters. The ionic composition of water
69 (anionic ratios of chloride, bicarbonate–carbonate and sulphate) appears to be an
70 especially important determinant of the distribution of saline species (e.g. in the brine
71 fly genus *Ephydra*; Herbst, 1999; 2001), and the effects of increasing salinity may vary
72 depending on ionic proportions (Zalizniak *et al.*, 2006). Thus, low to moderate saline
73 habitats host species with a limited osmoregulatory ability (hyperosmotic regulation and
74 osmoconforming) and broad or nonspecific ion regulation capacity. On the other hand,

75 high tolerance to salinity stress (hypoosmotic regulation) and specific ionic regulation
76 abilities are expected in species occurring in much more saline habitats (Herbst, 2001).
77 In this sense, solute composition, along with salinity, thermal regime and habitat
78 stability may provide a template that shapes the distribution of many organisms
79 inhabiting saline systems (Herbst & Bromley, 1984). However, factors other than the
80 direct effects of salinity tolerance are rarely considered by researchers studying inland
81 saline biotas when attempting to explain species distributions along salinity gradients
82 (Ward, 1992).

83 Some salinity tolerance information for water boatmen (mostly regarding adults of the
84 species) is available (e.g. Kelts, 1979; Catharine & Scudder, 1979; Cooper *et al.*, 1987;
85 Velasco *et al.*, 2006; Van De Meutter *et al.*, 2010). In general, species show a wider
86 salinity tolerance in the laboratory than the salinity range in which they occur in the
87 field, and mainly inhabit the more saline water bodies that they can tolerate in order to
88 avoid interspecific competition (Herbst, 2001). However, the degree to which laboratory
89 measures of tolerance reflect the field distributions of biota is uncertain (Kefford *et al.*,
90 2004b), and field observations cannot establish a causal link (Underwood *et al.*, 2000).

91 In addition, although there has been previous study of salinity tolerances of several
92 adult *Sigara* species (Van De Meutter *et al.*, 2010), information on the salinity tolerance
93 of eggs and nymphal stages is still lacking. The presence of adults at a particular salinity
94 does not necessarily indicate that the species can complete its life cycle at that salinity.
95 Thus, defining salinity tolerances according to life stage is of high ecological concern to
96 improve knowledge about the breadth of salinity niches and determine what might be
97 the most vulnerable life-stage in terms of habitat occupation. The nymphs of a corixid,
98 *Trichocorixa verticalis verticalis* (Fieber, 1851), tolerate lower salinities than the adults
99 (Van de Meutter *et al.*, 2010), and a similar pattern has been reported for the eggs of

100 many other macroinvertebrate species in comparison to their adult counterparts (Kefford
101 *et al.*, 2004a; 2007). Therefore, salinity tolerance data from adult life-stages may
102 overestimate their overall species tolerance.

103 The present study aims to assess the significance of salinity and water chemistry in
104 habitat occupation of three corixid species that demonstrate different habitat preferences:
105 *Sigara nigrolineata nigrolineata* (Fieber, 1848) in freshwater streams, *Sigara scripta*
106 (Rambur, 1840) in hyposaline waters and *Sigara selecta* (Fieber, 1848) in mesosaline
107 and hypersaline waters. These species cover a wide salinity gradient that encompasses a
108 variety of anionic compositions (carbonate, sulphate and chloride-dominated waters).
109 Our aims were (a) to determine the realised niche in relation to saline and anionic
110 composition of each species from field data, (b) to compare these with their
111 fundamental niches as defined under standardised laboratory conditions for their three
112 life-stages (egg, nymph and adult) and (c) to identify differences in the physiological
113 tolerances of the three life-stages within and among species. We hypothesized (1) a
114 strong concordance between fundamental and realised niches, (2) that *S. selecta* would
115 show a wider salinity tolerance and would be more specialised to ionic compositions
116 than *S. scripta* and *S. nigrolineata*, the latter two having broad or nonspecific ion
117 regulation capacities, (3) that species inhabiting freshwater and hyposaline habitats
118 would be more tolerant of high sulphate than species inhabiting hypersaline habitats and
119 (4) that younger life-stages would be less tolerant of higher salinity levels than the
120 older/dominant life-stages, thus constraining the habitats where the species can
121 reproduce.

122

123 METHODS

124 *Studied species*

125 *Sigara selecta* occurs in brackish, saline aquatic systems distributed throughout western
126 Europe and northern Africa (Aukema & Rieger, 1995) and seems to be associated with
127 coastal lentic water bodies, at least in its Iberian distribution (Nieser *et al.*, 1994).
128 *Sigara scripta* is found in circum-Mediterranean countries and south-western Asia
129 (Aukema & Rieger, 1995), inhabiting ponds and pools in both freshwater and
130 hyposaline lotic systems (Carbonell *et al.*, 2011) and also occurring in brackish waters in
131 coastal areas (Moreno *et al.*, 1997; Van de Meutter *et al.*, 2010). *Sigara nigrolineata*
132 *nigrolineata* is widely spread over the Palaearctic Region (Aukema & Rieger, 1995) and
133 frequently inhabits freshwater ponds and pools in lotic and lentic systems (Millán *et al.*,
134 1988; Carbonell *et al.*, 2011).

135

136 *Field data*

137 Abundance records for the three species from 177 localities in the Iberian Peninsula
138 were gathered from the Aquatic Ecology Research Group's biodiversity database at the
139 University of Murcia (Carbonell *et al.*, 2011 and A. Millán *et al.*, unpublished data).
140 This database includes biological and environmental data obtained by sampling both
141 lentic and lotic aquatic systems since 1980, following a multihabitat protocol (Jáimez-
142 Cuéllar *et al.*, 2002). Macroinvertebrate samples were collected using hand nets
143 (pentagonal or triangular, 20 to 30 cm deep and 0.5 to 1 mm mesh).
144 To determine the realized niches in relation to conductivity and anionic composition,
145 four water variables were considered: electrical conductivity (EC) and carbonate,
146 sulphate and chloride concentrations (meq L⁻¹). Water electrical conductivity was
147 measured in the field with standard portable equipment (ECmeter, TetraComR, 325.
148 WTW GmbH, Weilheim, Bayern, Germany). Sulphate and chloride concentrations were
149 determined photometrically with Spectroquant, NOVA 60 kits (MERCK®. Darmstadt,

150 Hessen, Germany) while alkalinity was measured colorimetrically with an alkalinity test
151 (AQUAMERCK®. Darmstadt, Hessen, Germany).

152 The realised niche of the three species for conductivity and anionic composition were
153 assessed by applying the Outlying Mean Index (OMI) analysis (Dolédec *et al.*, 2000)
154 using the niche procedure in ADE-4 (Thioulouse *et al.*, 1997). The OMI, or species
155 marginality index, measures the distance between the mean habitat conditions used by
156 species (species centroid), and the mean habitat conditions of the sampling area (origin
157 of the niche hyperspace). OMI analysis places species along habitat conditions. The
158 position of the species depends on their niche deviation from a reference, which
159 represents neither the mean nor the most abundant species but rather a theoretical
160 ubiquitous species that tolerates the most general habitat conditions (i.e., a hypothetical
161 species uniformly distributed among habitat conditions). This analysis also calculates
162 niche breadth (tolerance) as a measure of the amplitude in the distribution of each
163 species along the sampled gradient. The OMI analysis was selected due to its
164 demonstrated suitability for the investigation of multidimensional niche breadths in the
165 presence of strong limiting factors (e.g. water salinity) (Dolédec *et al.*, 2000). Moreover,
166 the analysis provides a separation of species based on their niche characteristics. This
167 analysis has also been used in the study of species niche segregation (e.g. corixids, Van
168 de Meutter *et al.*, 2010, and benthic diatoms, Soinenen & Heino, 2007).

169 The species abundance and environmental variables were logarithmically transformed
170 prior to analysis. This analysis was performed in R v 2.7.2 for Windows

171

172 *Salinity and anionic tolerance tests*

173 Salinity and anionic tolerance tests for the three *Sigara* species were carried out in
174 controlled laboratory conditions following standard protocols (Kefford *et al.*, 2005;

175 2007). Adults and nymphs of the three studied species were collected in spring and
176 summer of 2011 at different sites within their southeast Iberian distribution area (Table
177 1). About 300 adults and nymphs of each species were collected with a hand net and
178 transported in containers with their original water to the laboratory. Before their use in
179 tolerance tests, adults from each species were kept for two days in a 7-L aquarium with
180 their original water and a natural substrate. They were held at 20-24°C to acclimatize to
181 laboratory conditions, and were fed frozen chironomid larvae daily. Nymphs were kept
182 in the same laboratory conditions, but fed with a mixture of natural epipelon, *Ruppia*
183 *maritima* and frozen chironomid larvae. Finally, to obtain eggs, males and females of
184 each species were placed in aquaria and allowed to reproduce and lay eggs on plastic
185 mesh that could be removed daily and transferred to test vials.

186 Tolerance tests covered the salinity range where water boatmen occur: freshwaters (<
187 0.5 g L⁻¹), hypo-saline waters (3-20 g L⁻¹), meso-saline waters (20-50 g L⁻¹) and hyper-
188 saline waters (> 50 g L⁻¹) (Montes & Martino, 1987). Five salinity treatments were
189 used: 0.3, 10, 25, 50 and 75 g L⁻¹, which correspond to 0.6, 16, 37, 74 and 100 mS cm⁻¹
190 EC, respectively. For each salinity concentration, four different anionic compositions
191 were tested, from chloride-dominated water (NaCl) to different chloride-sulphate
192 proportions (3NaCl:1SO₄Na₂; 2NaCl:1SO₄Na₂ and 1NaCl:1SO₄Na₂). The different
193 solutions were prepared by dissolving marine salt (Ocean Fish, Prodac®. Citadella Pd,
194 Italy) and sodium sulphate (Panreac®. Castellar del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain) in
195 distilled water.

196 After acclimatising, adults were placed individually in 50 mL aereated boxes filled with
197 solutions under controlled conditions (20 ± 1 °C, 12 h light: 12 h dark photoperiod, light
198 intensity of 15 µmol m⁻² s⁻¹, without food) in an environmental chamber (SANYO
199 MLR-351. SANYO electric Co., Ltd, Moriguchi City, Osaka, Japan).

200 A total of 210 adults from each species were used in the experiment (ten individuals x
201 five conductivities x four anionic compositions + ten control individuals). The tolerated
202 control mortality rate was 20 %. Survival was monitored daily for one week.
203 Conductivity and dissolved oxygen were monitored daily and did not vary significantly
204 over time.
205 The same number of nymphs and eggs from each species were used as for adults.
206 Nymphs (third or fourth instars) and eggs (less than 24 hours old) were placed
207 individually in glass vials (5 mL solution) under the same experimental conditions as
208 adults. The nymph's survival was monitored at 24 h intervals for 48 h, and eggs until
209 hatching.
210 ANOVA was used to analyse the effects of conductivity and anionic composition on the
211 survival time of adults and nymphs, and the hatching time of eggs for each species.
212 Previous analyses showed no differences in tolerance between sexes in adults (J.A.
213 Carbonell *et al.*, unpublished data). Differences in survival after 48 hours between
214 adults and nymphs for each species were also analysed using ANOVA. Because some
215 data did not satisfy all ANOVA assumptions, a more conservative approach was
216 employed ($p \leq 0.01$). A post-hoc analysis with Bonferroni correction was implemented
217 to identify significant differences in the response variables among treatments
218 (Underwood, 1997; Rutherford, 2001). All statistical analyses were conducted using
219 SPSS for Windows, Rel. 15.0.1. 2006. Chicago: SPSS Inc.

220

221 RESULTS

222 *Realised niches*

223 Conductivity and anionic 'position niches' (OMI) and niche breadths (Tol) obtained by
224 OMI analyses for the three species are shown in Table 2. *Sigara scripta* was distributed

225 across a range of 0.05-43 mS cm⁻¹ and had the lowest OMI value with regards to
226 conductivity and had an intermediate value for niche breadth. This means that its niche
227 is midway in the total conductivity range in which the three species are distributed, and
228 that it selects waters with intermediate conductivities. *Sigara nigrolineata* showed the
229 highest OMI and lowest niche breadth, being an exclusive inhabitant of freshwater
230 aquatic systems (0.02-18 mS cm⁻¹). *Sigara selecta* showed an intermediate OMI value
231 and the highest niche breadth, being able to inhabit the entire sampled conductivity
232 gradient (Figure 1A). In relation to anionic compositions, *S. nigrolineata* displayed the
233 highest OMI and niche breadth values, while *S. selecta* demonstrated the lowest (Table
234 2). *Sigara nigrolineata* showed a preference for carbonated waters, but also showed a
235 high tolerance for anionic composition within the narrow conductivity range in which
236 they occurred. The niche of *S. scripta* overlapped in part with that of *S. selecta*,
237 although the former seemed to select sulphated waters, unlike *S. selecta*, which selected
238 chlorided waters (Figure 1B).

239

240 *Fundamental niches*

241 *Adults*

242 The effects of conductivity on adult survival time were significant for all three species
243 (Figure 2A and Table 3), while anionic composition and the interaction of conductivity
244 and anionic composition had significant effects only for *S. scripta* (Table 3), which
245 showed its longest survival time in sulphated treatments (Figure 3A). *Sigara*
246 *nigrolineata* had the longest survival time at 0.6 mS cm⁻¹, while *S. scripta* showed
247 optima at 0.6 and 16 mS cm⁻¹ (Figure 2A). The most tolerant species, *S. selecta*, was
248 able to survive along the entire tested conductivity gradient, but its optimum range
249 seemed to be between 16 and 37 mS cm⁻¹ treatments (Figure 2A).

250

251 *Nymphs*

252 Conductivity also had significant effects on survival time of nymphs (Figure 2B and
253 Table 4), and again only the interaction of conductivity and anionic composition had a
254 significant effect on *S. scripta* (Table 4). Nymphs of *S. nigrolineata* and *S. scripta*
255 survived at 0.6 and 16 mS cm⁻¹ treatments, with the latter as the upper limit, while *S.*
256 *selecta* survived up to 37 mS cm⁻¹ (Figure 2B). No significant differences were found
257 between nymphs and adults for survival time (measured for 48h period) for *S.*
258 *nigrolineata* ($F = 1.537, p = 0.191$), while for *S. scripta* ($F = 10.944, p < 0.001$) and *S.*
259 *selecta* ($F = 28.069, p < 0.001$) the salinity tolerance of the nymphs was lower than for
260 the adults. At 0.6 mS cm⁻¹, *S. scripta* nymphs showed similar results to the adults, with
261 survival time increasing as the sulphate proportion rose, but this pattern was not evident
262 at 16 mS cm⁻¹ (Figure 3B).

263

264 *Eggs*

265 As for the other life-stages, the effect of conductivity was significant in egg hatching
266 times of the three species, while anionic composition only showed significant effects for
267 *S. selecta*, and the interaction of conductivity and anionic composition had a significant
268 effect on *S. nigrolineata* (see Table 5). *Sigara nigrolineata* only hatched at 0.6 mS cm⁻¹
269 (Figure 2C) with an average hatching time of 12.07 days, being significantly longer at
270 2NaCl:1SO₄Na₂. *Sigara scripta* eggs hatched at 0.6 and 16 mS cm⁻¹ with no differences
271 between conductivity treatments (mean hatching time of 14.37 days). Eggs of *S. selecta*
272 hatched at conductivities up to 74 mS cm⁻¹, presenting the longest hatching time of the
273 three species (mean hatching time of 18.5 days). At 74 mS cm⁻¹ treatment, the mean

274 hatching time of *S. selecta* eggs was significantly longer than in the lower
275 conductivities, decreasing significantly with increase sulphate proportion (Figure 4).

276

277 DISCUSSION

278 We found strong concordance between the tolerances of three *Sigara* species for salinity
279 and anionic composition as revealed by field observations and laboratory experiments.

280 The most tolerant species, *Sigara selecta*, is able to inhabit hypersaline waters around
281 128 mS cm⁻¹, while the least tolerant, *S. nigrolineata*, occurs principally in freshwaters

282 and is rarely found in hyposaline waters. However, *S. scripta*, with an intermediate
283 salinity tolerance, sometimes coexists with each of the other species, with its

284 conductivity niche overlapping that of *S. selecta* at the upper limits and that of *S.*

285 *nigrolineata* at the lower limits, although the three species never all occurred together in

286 one location. It is likely that *S. scripta* is an osmoconformer, like other corixid species

287 that occur in hyposaline waters such as *Cenocorixa bifida* and *Cenocorixa expleta*

288 (Scudder, 1976). These species have hyperosmotic regulation in freshwaters conditions

289 up to a particular osmotic concentration of the external medium (the osmotic

290 concentration of their haemolymph). Above that osmotic concentration they turn into

291 conformers, with the osmotic concentration of the haemolymph exactly matching that of

292 the external medium until a lethal concentration is reached (Bradley, 2008). Such a

293 regulation mechanism would restrict the persistence of *S. scripta* under more saline

294 conditions. *Sigara selecta* is able to hyposmoregulate, as occurs in other species from

295 hypersaline waters such as *S. stagnalis* and *Trichocorixa* (Tones & Hammer, 1975; Jang

296 & Tullis, 1980). Although comparative studies of the structural and physiological

297 mechanisms involved in osmoregulation have not been carried out on the three studied

298 species, differences in the structure and function of the midgut, Malpighian tubules,

299 labial epidermis and chloride cells on the exposed body surface of species could play an
300 important role in these processes, as is the case for other corixids that inhabit saline
301 waters (Scudder, 1976). Future studies of osmoregulation mechanisms and ionic
302 regulation for these species will be needed to verify these assumptions.

303 In the tolerance tests, *S. scripta* and *S. selecta* were able to survive in freshwater
304 conditions. The survival ability of *S. selecta*, the most common Iberian corixid in
305 hypersaline waters (Velasco et al., 2006; Carbonell et al., 2011), under non-saline
306 conditions implies that this species is not a strict halophilic species (halophilic -
307 surviving only in saline environments) as occurs in other saline water bug species
308 (Tones & Hammer, 1975). The fact that *S. selecta* inhabits mainly hypersaline waters
309 might therefore be explained by factors other than purely physiological ones. Their
310 broad physiological tolerance can provide a chemical refuge from interspecific
311 pressures, such as competition or predation. Thus, for example, a marked difference in
312 susceptibility to mite parasitism between two closely saline boatmen species,
313 *Cenocorixa expleta* and *C. bifida*, excludes the first species from fresh and low salinity
314 lakes where mites are abundant, and forces them to select the most saline lakes
315 (Scudder, 1983).

316 Our realised niche studies in relation to anionic composition showed narrow *S. selecta*
317 and *S. scripta* niches, indicating lower tolerance or more specific anion regulation in
318 these species than for *S. nigrolineata*, which seems to select carbonated waters. In
319 addition, the broad chemical niche of *S. nigrolineata* also indicates a low ionic
320 specificity within the narrow range of conductivity in which it occurs. In contrast, *S.*
321 *selecta* selects chloride waters, whereas *S. scripta* inhabits sulphated waters, although
322 their niches partially overlapped. This suggests that species inhabiting inland hyposaline
323 waters, such as *S. scripta*, show higher tolerance to sulphate. This anion, together with

324 carbonates, is more abundant in this kind of water body than in coastal ones, which have
325 a similar chemical composition to seawater with sodium chloride as the predominant
326 salt (Moreno *et al.*, 2009). On the other hand, the specificity of *S. selecta* for chloride-
327 dominated waters might explain the common occurrence of this species in coastal zones
328 throughout its global distribution (Nieser *et al.*, 1994; Aukema & Rieger, 1995). Even
329 when occupying continental saline waters, its habitats contain mainly sodium chloride.
330 These results are in general agreement with the anionic tolerance values obtained in
331 laboratory experiments and with our predictions. Thus, our results support the
332 hypothesis that species inhabiting freshwaters are not expected to be specialised to
333 specific anionic compositions, because water chemistry at lower salinities is not a
334 significantly stressful factor, whereas as water salinity increases species would be
335 expected to be more specialised to ionic composition (Herbst, 2001).

336 Nymphs of *S. scripta* and *S. selecta* showed reduced tolerance and survival times
337 compared to adults, which is common among saline boatmen species, such as
338 *Tricorixa verticalis verticalis* (Van de Meutter *et al.*, 2010), as well as many other
339 freshwater macroinvertebrate taxa (Kefford *et al.*, 2004a; 2007). It has also been shown
340 that differences in salinity tolerance between younger and adult life-stages are of a
341 greater magnitude in freshwater insects than in other aquatic macroinvertebrates such as
342 macrocrustaceans or gastropods (Kefford *et al.*, 2004a). In freshwater species, the
343 younger life-stages could be more sensitive to salinity because nymphs may regulate
344 their haemolymph at a lower osmolality than the adults. As a consequence, they become
345 osmoconformers at a lower salinity. Moreover, the maximum osmolality of the
346 haemolymph that nymphs can tolerate might be lower than in adults (Kefford *et al.*,
347 2007). These physiological differences among younger and adult life-stages might be
348 more important in species living in saline waters.

349 *Sigara nigrolineata* eggs hatched only in freshwater conditions, thereby showing lower
350 tolerance than adults and nymphs, which were able to tolerate hyposaline waters.
351 However, for the saline species, the salinity tolerance of eggs was similar to (*S. scripta*)
352 or higher than the nymphs (*S. selecta*). It is notable that *S. selecta* has been found
353 breeding in the field at a salinity of 55 g L⁻¹ (Velasco *et al.*, 2006) and it is known that
354 eggs of *Trichocorixa verticalis verticalis* hatch at conductivities up to 73 mS cm⁻¹
355 (Kelts, 1979). *Sigara selecta*, together with *S. stagnalis* (Leach, 1817) and *T. v.*
356 *verticalis*, are the only known Hemiptera that can live and reproduce successfully in
357 hypersaline waters (Tones, 1977).
358 Eggs of saline species take longer to hatch than eggs of freshwater species (*S.*
359 *nigrolineata* eggs took an average of 10 days, *S. scripta* eggs 15 days and *S. selecta*
360 eggs about 18 days). The longer hatching time needed for saline species might suggest
361 that part of the egg resources are used to retain the osmolality of their fluids, thus
362 increasing osmoregulatory energy demands (Schowalter, 2011). Osmoregulation is an
363 energetically costly process that increases with external osmolarity (Oren, 1999), which
364 could also explain the longer hatching times of *S. selecta* eggs at the upper limit of their
365 conductivity tolerance in comparison to their optimum (between 16 and 37 mS cm⁻¹).
366 Like *S. selecta*, there are several species whose eggs take longer to hatch when they are
367 exposed to higher salinities, including the limpet *Burnupia stenochorias* (Kefford *et al.*,
368 2004a) and the waterbug *Notonecta glauca* (Komnick & Wichard, 1975). However, the
369 relationship between egg development period and salinity is not uniform across taxa,
370 and whether such delays have ecological implications is not known (Kefford *et al.*,
371 2007). A trade-off exists between stress tolerance and competitive ability (Wilson &
372 Keddy, 1986). Generally, the costs of survival on other traits such as reproduction also
373 should be considered, because a trade-off between ecophysiological stress and

374 reproductive investment might prevail in stressed populations (P'etillon *et al.*, 2011). As
375 a result, the longer hatching time of *S. selecta* eggs found in this study in comparison
376 with the less saline tolerant species could diminish their competitive ability.
377 Finally, anionic composition showed significant effects on egg hatching times only for
378 *S. selecta*. At 74 mS cm⁻¹, the hatching time for this species was shorter in sulphated
379 waters than in chloride-dominated waters. This result could be interpreted as an
380 adaptive response of *S. selecta* to drought and/or a mechanism to deal with
381 unfavourable conditions that allows them to synchronise their life cycle with favourable
382 habitat conditions. In the temporary saline environments that it inhabits, such as
383 estuarine habitats or salt marshes, as water disappears by evaporation, salinity increases
384 and the concentration of dissolved substances changes, following the normal trend from
385 carbonate to sulphatochloride to chloride water as calcium carbonate and subsequently
386 calcium sulphate and possibly sodium sulphate are precipitated (Williams, 2006).
387 Increased sulphate could be a stimulus to rapid egg development and hatching before
388 lethal limits are reached. On the other hand, the resistance of *S. selecta* eggs to
389 desiccation has not been studied, although it has been shown that other corixid species
390 inhabiting hypersaline waters, including some *Trichocorixa* species, have dormant eggs
391 that are resistant to partial desiccation, freezing and high sulphide production (Tones &
392 Hammer, 1975; Kelts, 1979).

393

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TABLES

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Table 1. Collection site information (geographical coordinates and mean conductivity) for tolerance laboratory tests.

Species	Sample location	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Conductivity (mS cm ⁻¹)
<i>S. nigrolineata</i>	Corneros River, Lorca, Murcia	37° 42' N	1° 54' W	530	1.26
<i>S. scripta</i>	Chícamo River, Abanilla, Murcia	38° 11' N	1° 03' W	150	12.9
<i>S. selecta</i>	Barranco del Diablo, Molina de Segura, Murcia	38° 07' N	1° 08' W	140	48.3

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Table 2. Conductivity range of natural habitats, outlying mean index (OMI) and niche breadth (Tol) of each *Sigara* species along the sampled gradient in conductivity and anionic composition. OMI values indicate the distance between the mean habitat used by species and the mean habitat conditions of the sampled area. *P* values indicate whether the OMI is significantly different from the mean habitat conditions in the dataset.

Species	Conductivity range (mS cm ⁻¹)	Conductivity			Anionic composition		
		OMI	Tol	<i>P</i>	OMI	Tol	<i>P</i>
<i>S. nigrolineata</i>	0.02-18	0.3222	0.0293	0.0120	3.8385	0.3279	0.0010
<i>S. scripta</i>	0.05-43	0.1279	0.1003	0.0090	2.0484	0.0126	0.4376
<i>S. selecta</i>	0.3-128	0.1907	1.4327	0.0010	1.8913	0.0001	0.8292

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Table 3. Effects of conductivity and anionic composition on survival times of *Sigara* adults.

Species	Effect	df	F	P
<i>S. nigrolineata</i>	Full model	19	31.102	0.000
	Intercept	1	544.500	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	1.997	0.116
	Conductivity	4	141.438	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	1.599	0.095
	Error	180		
<i>S. scripta</i>	Full model	19	20.077	0.000
	Intercept	1	323.670	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	7.673	0.000
	Conductivity	4	82.331	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	2.427	0.006
	Error	180		
<i>S. selecta</i>	Full model	19	10.622	0.000
	Intercept	1	741.222	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	1.972	0.120
	Conductivity	4	44.667	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	1.436	0.153
	Error	180		

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Table 4. Effects of conductivity and anionic composition on survival times of *Sigara* nymphs.

Species	Effect	df	F	P
<i>S. nigrolineata</i>	Full model	19	65.925	0.000
	Intercept	1	824.005	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	0.161	0.922
	Conductivity	4	312.322	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	0.234	0.996
	Error	180		
<i>S. scripta</i>	Full model	19	36.471	0.000
	Intercept	1	437.533	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	2.677	0.049
	Conductivity	4	164.091	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	2.380	0.007
	Error	180		
<i>S. selecta</i>	Full model	19	24.272	0.000
	Intercept	1	620.735	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	2.798	0.042
	Conductivity	4	110.103	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	1.029	0.424
	Error	180		

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Table 5. Effects of conductivity and anionic composition on hatching times of *Sigara* eggs.

Species	Effect	df	F	P
<i>S. nigrolineata</i>	Full model	19	54.321	0.000
	Intercept	1	18645.047	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	2.680	0.048
	Conductivity	4	247.975	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	2.680	0.002
	Error	180		
<i>S. scripta</i>	Full model	19	27.090	0.000
	Intercept	1	7765.656	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	1.704	0.168
	Conductivity	4	123.469	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	1.309	0.216
	Error	180		
<i>S. selecta</i>	Full model	19	13.416	0.000
	Intercept	1	7797.542	0.000
	Anionic composition	3	5.049	0.002
	Conductivity	4	54.415	0.000
	Anionic composition x conductivity	12	1.842	0.045
	Error	180		

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639 FIGURE LEGENDS

640

641 **Figure 1.** (A) Realised niche breadths of the three *Sigara* species in relation to water
642 conductivity (x-axis represents range of conductivity in the study area. *Mean
643 conductivity value of the sampling sites). (B) Niche breadths (ellipses) of the species in
644 relation to anionic water composition (domination by different chemicals represented by
645 arrows, and localities by spots) obtained from OMI analyses.

646

647 **Figure 2.** Average \pm SE survival time of adults, nymphs and eggs in conductivity
648 treatments. Significant differences determined by post-hoc analysis employing
649 Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows. Numbers above bars - differences in
650 survival time among species in every conductivity treatment. Letters above bars -
651 differences in survival time among conductivity treatments for one species.

652

653 **Figure 3.** Average \pm SE survival time of (A) adults of *S. scripta* and (B) nymphs in
654 relation to conductivity and anionic composition treatments. Significant differences
655 determined by post-hoc analysis employing Bonferroni correction are indicated as
656 follows. Numbers above bars - differences in survival time among anionic compositions
657 in every conductivity treatment. Letters in legend - significant differences in survival
658 time among anionic composition treatments.

659

660 **Figure 4.** Average \pm SE hatching time of *S. selecta* eggs in relation to conductivity and
661 anionic composition treatments. Significant differences determined by post-hoc analysis
662 employing Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows. Numbers above bars -
663 differences in survival time among anionic compositions in every conductivity
664 treatment. Letters in legend - significant differences in survival time among anionic
665 composition treatments.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4